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Fidelity of Implementation (FOI) of the Grade 10 English Curriculum: Developing a FOI Framework for Curriculum Delivery

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Abstract

Fidelity of implementation (FOI) is employed to probe into the implementation of the curriculum by English teachers as intended by developers through the curriculum guide. This explanatory-sequential paper sought to probe into the fidelity of implementation practice of high school English teachers using the dimensions of adherence, duration and quality of delivery. Data were gathered using the Curriculum Fidelity of Implementation Survey-Questionnaire, focus group discussion and document analysis. Data analyses were conducted using quantitative and qualitative approaches. Findings revealed that teachers mostly implement the curriculum with average adherence but cited several reasons for not accomplishing the learning competencies. Overall, high quality of delivery was observed and the required time allotment for the Grade 10 English subject was implemented; however, these did not translate to the full implementation of the curriculum. Reasons such as lack of orientation on the learning competencies, intervening and other-teaching related activities, professional development programs during class days, among others resort to teachers' backlogged discussion of the competencies. Implications of and recommendation for the study were provided for future researchers and empirical discussion.

Keywords: Curriculum Fidelity of Implementation, English Curriculum, Adherence, Exposure, Quality of Delivery

1. Introduction

Fidelity of Implementation (FOI) is a critical factor in ensuring the successful delivery of educational programs and curricula. It refers to the degree to which a program or intervention is implemented as intended by its developers (Dane & Schneider, 1998; O'Donnell, 2008). When a curriculum is implemented with high fidelity, it increases the likelihood that the intended learning outcomes will be achieved (Century et al., 2010). The concept is widely recognized and utilized in the field of education and curriculum development to ensure the faithful implementation of educational programs. Research on FOI helps assess the effectiveness of curriculum implementation strategies, identify factors that influence fidelity, and inform improvements in educational practices.

Curriculum implementation is an important topic, but it is frequently examined from the standpoint of national issues (Nevenglosky, 2019). Nonetheless, there has been an increasing interest in implementation research to examine classroom implementation, specifically with regard to instructors' adherence to the curriculum. Curriculum fidelity of implementation refers to the existence and level of actual implementation done by teachers as compared to the written curriculum (Mihalic, 2002; Santacrose et al., 2004; Furtz et al., 2008). Studies about curriculum fidelity have been divided into two perspectives: the traditional and the innovative approaches. Generally, traditionalist accounts are pro-curriculum fidelity while the innovative lenses focus more on the adaptation side. Traditionalists believe that the curriculum must be fully implemented. Innovative FOI researchers, however, point that the curriculum must be adapted in the school. Over the years, these two have been mixed and have been argued by researchers (Dusenbury, et al., 2003, as cited in Bumen et al., 2014). The third view is the most prominently used by curriculum researchers. Despite these diversities of opinion, it is acknowledged that curriculum fidelity must be studied.

This study aims to examine the single and most important factor in curriculum implementation (International Task Force on Teachers for Education 2030) discourse, English teachers who are teaching Grade 10. Grade 10 is the last key level in the junior high school (JHS) curriculum and it is expected that by this stage, all competencies required for JHS are, if not completely, covered.

There are three curriculum fidelity of implementation dimensions explored in this study: adherence, exposure and quality of delivery. *Adherence* refers to the extent to which the curriculum is delivered as stated in the written curriculum and implementing appropriate scope and sequence (Dusenbury et al, 2003). Adherence is necessary in FOI because it shows teachers' faithfulness to the curriculum they implement. The K to 12 English curriculum - through its objectives, competencies, and standards – articulates how it must be implemented. Adherence determines the ways teachers implement the curriculum. For example, in discussing a lesson on subject-verb agreement, a teacher needs to review the curriculum guide to deliver the lesson. Without a familiarity with the English curriculum guide, it is difficult to determine how teachers adhere to curriculum implementation. *Exposure* refers to the length of session (i.e. 60 minutes), duration (i.e. 2 weeks, 1 quarter) and frequency (i.e. daily) in the curriculum that is delivered by the teachers (Dusenbury et al., 2003). In employing the sub-dimensions of exposure, the K to 12 English Language curriculum will be used as primary reference. *Quality of delivery* pertains to how the teacher plans, prepares, delivers the lessons, and assesses student learning outcomes in the classroom (Dusenbury et al., 2003). Researchers need to further investigate how teachers competently teach English lessons in the classroom. For example, an English teacher provides drills and independent practice activities to the learners in teaching a lesson on nouns.

2. Literature Review

Teachers' age and curriculum FOI have different results in research literature. Süer & Kinay (2022) found that younger teachers are more receptive to a curriculum as compared to their seasoned teacher counterparts. This can be attributed to the new opportunities that are experienced first by younger teachers in their professional teaching practice. On the other hand, some research found that there is no strong link between teachers' age and curriculum FOI (Aslan & Erden, 2020; Christison & Murray, 2021).

Similarly, teaching experience and curriculum FOI, Boyd et al. (2021) found no correlation between years of teaching and program structure. Other factors interplayed with curriculum FOI such as teachers' beliefs and alignment to the curriculum program objectives (Anteneh & Anshu, 2024). Seasoned teachers, who have undergone numerous and quality professional training, are able to deliver the curriculum with higher fidelity. These professional development trainings are targeted towards the teachers' pedagogical needs. Interestingly, teachers with more experience find it challenging to adapt to curriculum objectives. This results in lower fidelity scores (Pennington et al., 2020).

Early research on curriculum fidelity (Garet et al., 2001 & Penuel et al., 2007) has emphasized that reliance on length of teaching does not necessarily guarantee higher curriculum fidelity. While older teachers have established their own teaching skills, empirical evidence points to their resistance to new curriculum principles and going beyond their comfort zones. On the other hand, experienced teachers are more aware of adjustments and strategies they can conduct in implementing the curriculum in their classrooms.

Teaching, historically employing more women, provides discussion on gender and curriculum FOI. Considering contexts, Vázquez-Cano et al. (2023) recommended that male teachers prioritize adherence and lesson sequence as compared to female teachers, who focus on nurturing a conducive learning environment. This key factor is substantial in planning professional learning development focusing on curriculum implementation, with priorities on delivery of lessons and learning environment.

With options for management and other-related roles, teaching position underscores that school leadership roles play an influential factor in increasing curriculum fidelity. Teachers, under the leadership of middle managers who provide support and guidance, were found to have higher curriculum fidelity of implementation Gelmez-Burakgazi, S. (2020). Other findings have also supported studies. Creating a shared sense of accountability and supporting classroom teachers yield high curriculum scores and increases teachers' sense of motivation and morale.

3. Research Questions

The study aimed to determine the fidelity of implementation of the English curriculum by Grade 10 teachers. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the Grade 10 English teachers in terms of:
 - 1.1. type of school affiliation,
 - 1.2. age of teachers,
 - 1.3. gender of teachers,
 - 1.4. teaching position,
 - 1.5. number of years in teaching, and
 - 1.6. highest educational attainment?
2. What is the curriculum fidelity of implementation by the Grade 10 English teachers in terms of the following dimensions:
 - 2.1. adherence,
 - 2.2. exposure, and
 - 2.3. quality of delivery?
3. Is there a significant difference in the curriculum fidelity of implementation of the Grade 10 English teachers when grouped according to the teachers' demographic profile?
4. Is there a significant difference between the curriculum fidelity of implementation of the Grade 10 English teachers per school and their school performance in the National Achievement Test?
5. What challenges did the teachers experience in the curriculum fidelity implementation in the three dimensions?
6. What framework can be developed based on the findings of the study?

4. Participants

The preliminary step in the collection of data was the request for the National Achievement Test 2018 results in Grade 10 from Region 3's top five (5) performing public and (5) private schools and lowest ten (5) performing public and (5) private schools based on their mean percentage scores. The sample schools will be 20 in total.

The participants included teachers with at least 1 year of teaching, English major, handles English subjects/teaching load, teach in either/or public or private schools, were already teachers in 2018. This study was

conducted in Region III, Philippines where the selected public and private high schools are situated. English teachers in Grade 10 were the teacher-participants for school year 2023-2024.

5. Methodology

This study utilized mixed methods using explanatory sequential research design. Using the Curriculum Fidelity of Implementation Survey Questionnaire, the teacher-participants were asked questions from a pool of curriculum FOI dimensions to produce the numerical results. The gathered data from the survey-questionnaire was employed particularly in establishing the significant relationship between the teacher-participants' characteristics and their fidelity to implementation of the English curriculum standards. As qualitative research, this study employed document analyses based on Grade 10 Curriculum Guide and focus group discussions. These supplemented the numerical results from the quantitative design. Alongside this, document analyses of other pertinent records were also analyzed such as lesson logs/plans, classroom assessment, and classroom observation ratings.

6. Findings and Discussion

Demographic profile of teachers

The sample teachers in the study are mostly from public schools and are aged 22-26 years old. Majority of the teachers are female educators and are entry-level teachers. In terms of teaching experience, the sample teachers have been in professional practice for one to five years and have taken Master's degree units.

Curriculum fidelity of implementation – adherence dimension

Table 1: Curriculum fidelity of implementation of the Grade 10 English teachers in terms of adherence

Code	Quarter (Q)	Learning competency	M	SD	Verbal interpretation
2.1.1	Q1	Use information from news reports, speeches, informative talks, panel discussions, etc. in everyday conversations and exchanges	2.97	0.72	Average Adherence
2.1.2	Q1	Determine the effect of textual aids like advance organizers, titles, non-linear illustrations, etc. on the understanding of a text.	3.04	0.71	Average Adherence
2.1.3	Q1	Appraise the unity of plot, setting and characterization in a material viewed to achieve the writer's purpose	2.78	0.75	Average Adherence
2.1.4	Q1	Compare and contrast the contents of the materials viewed with outside sources of information in terms of accessibility and effectiveness	3.14	0.85	Average Adherence
2.1.5	Q1	Employ analytical listening in problem solving	2.78	0.73	Average Adherence

2.1.6	Q1	Evaluate and make judgments about a range of texts using a set of criteria e.g. comparing arguments on the same topic, critiquing a short story	2.74	0.65	Average Adherence
2.1.7	Q1	Evaluate spoken texts using given criteria, e.g. fluency, tone, cohesion, correctness	2.92	0.80	Average Adherence
2.1.8	Q2	Observe the language of research, campaigns, and advocacies	2.51	0.68	Average Adherence
2.1.9	Q2	Identify key structural elements, e.g.: • Exposition - Statement of position, • Arguments, • Restatement of Positions and language features of an argumentative text, e.g.: • modal verbs: should, must, might, and modal adverbs: usually, probably, etc.; • attitudes expressed through evaluative language; • conjunctions or connectives to link ideas: because, therefore, on the other hand, etc.; • declarative statements; • rhetorical questions; passive voice	2.98	0.77	Average Adherence
2.1.10	Q2	Formulate a statement of opinion or assertion	3.40	0.49	Average Adherence
2.1.11	Q2	Formulate claims of fact, policy, and value	3.42	0.50	Average Adherence
2.1.12	Q2	Write an exposition or discussion on a familiar issue to include key structural elements and language features	3.00	0.68	Average Adherence
2.1.13	Q2	Deliver a prepared or impromptu talk on an issue employing the techniques in public speaking	3.09	0.59	Average Adherence
2.1.14	Q2	Compose texts which include multimodal elements	3.00	0.68	Average Adherence
2.1.15	Q2	Compose an argumentative essay	3.00	0.69	Average Adherence

2.1.16	Q2	Use a variety of informative, persuasive, and argumentative writing techniques	3.00	0.68	Average Adherence
2.1.17	Q2	Compose an independent critique of a chosen selection	3.00	0.68	Average Adherence
2.1.18	Q3	Critique a literary selection based on the following approaches: - structuralist/formalist - moralist - Marxist - feminist -historical -reader-response	2.77	0.72	Average Adherence
2.1.19	Q4	Distinguish technical terms used in research	2.99	0.88	Average Adherence
2.1.20	Q4	Give technical and operational definitions	2.59	0.63	Average Adherence
2.1.21	Q4	Give expanded definition of words	3.45	0.50	Average Adherence
2.1.22	Q4	Observe correct grammar in making definitions	3.46	0.50	Average Adherence
2.1.23	Q4	Compose a research report on a relevant social issue	3.05	0.62	Average Adherence
Total			3.00	0.674191	Average Adherence

Legend:

High adherence	3.50-4.00
Average adherence	2.50-3.49
Inadequate adherence	1.50-2.49
Low adherence	1.00-1.49

Table 1 shows the fidelity of implementation of the sample teachers for adherence. Adherence refers to the teachers' implementation of the curriculum as intended. The Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) were the decongested version of the curricular guide which teachers comply with and teach in their classrooms. Although teachers adhered to average in terms of adherence, there were some observations cited such as the teachers' reliance on the teaching modules as reference for their daily lesson logs. Learning modules were employed during the height of the CoVid-19 pandemic as part of the different learning modalities that were offered by the education department. Data show that all the most essential learning competencies were implemented with average adherence (range: 2.50-3.49) of the teachers. This points to all the MELCs for implementation by the Grade 10 teachers. Average adherence refers to teachers' coverage of 3-4 needed learning competencies. Teachers explained that their implementation focused only on interpreting the competency themselves and results in different content in the classrooms. As mentioned by Teacher 1-4 (2023), *"I think that focusing the curriculum on real applications is very effective. Students like to use the language in a practical context, which makes learning more interesting."* Majority of the sampled public school teachers employ the learning modules developed during the height of the CoVid-19 pandemic when face-to-face classes were not available while private school teachers used both textbook and modular references. The learning logs/plans of teachers also have different interpretations of what content is appropriate for the most essential learning competency.

Hardman and A-Rahman (2014, cited in Barrot, 2018) affirmed that basic education English teachers struggle in implementing the curriculum due its lack of the comprehensive articulation. While there are only twenty-five (25) MELCs required for the Grade 10 were implemented by the teachers, some expectations were not implemented as evidenced by the different interpretation in their lesson planning and execution.

Curriculum fidelity of implementation – exposure dimension

Table 2: Curriculum fidelity of implementation of the Grade 10 English teachers in terms of exposure

Curriculum FOI dimension	N	M	SD	Verbal Interpretation
Exposure	78	3.82	.386	High Exposure

Table 2 shows the fidelity of implementation of the Grade 10 English teachers in relation to exposure. Data reveal that the sample teachers have a high (.38) fidelity of implementation in exposure. Exposure refers to the teachers' fidelity to implementation in terms of time allotment. This is necessary to comply with classroom teachers as they abide with a teacher schedule equivalent to the subject they teach.

Teacher 3-5 (2023) emphasized that “*The curriculum is a little demanding and covering all the topics for the subject time is difficult, especially with too many students.*”

Curriculum fidelity of implementation - quality of delivery dimension

Table 3: Curriculum fidelity of implementation of the Grade 10 English teachers in terms of quality of delivery

Quality of delivery criteria	Statement	M	SD	Verbal interpretation
Teaching/ Ethics	I maintain high ethical standards in interaction with students, colleagues, and parents.	3.82	0.39	High Quality of Delivery
Teaching/ Classroom Environment	I convey information clearly and foster a positive learning environment.	3.64	0.48	High Quality of Delivery
Teaching/ Inclusivity	I adapt teaching methods to meet the diverse needs of students including those with different learning styles and abilities.	3.58	0.50	High Quality of Delivery
Teaching/ Methods & Strategies	I utilize varied and appropriate teaching methods, strategies, and techniques that engage students in learning.	3.58	0.50	High Quality of Delivery
Teaching/ Instructional Delivery	I provide satisfactory instructional delivery based on their performance scores.	3.58	0.50	High Quality of Delivery
Teaching/ Technology Use	I incorporate technology that can enhance learning.	3.56	0.49	High Quality of Delivery

Teaching/ Inclusivity	I respect diverse backgrounds and cultures among students for an inclusive learning environment.	3.56	0.49	High Quality of Delivery
Teaching/ Assessment	I design fair and accurate assessments to measure student learning and provide constructive feedback for improvement.	3.55	0.50	High Quality of Delivery
Teaching/ Learner Participation	I encourage active participation and interest in the subject matter.	3.50	0.50	High Quality of Delivery
Teaching/ Professional Development	I continuously update my teaching skills and stay informed about educational trends and research.	3.49	0.50	Average Quality of Delivery
Teaching/ Instructional Material	I employ instructional materials/resources that are appropriate with the curricular standards.	3.45	0.50	Average Quality of Delivery
Teaching/ Classroom Management	I create a well-organized and disciplined classroom environment for effective teaching.	3.45	0.50	Average Quality of Delivery
Curriculum Understanding	I have a deep understanding of the subject matter to effectively convey information to my students.	3.45	0.50	Average Quality of Delivery
Curriculum Understanding	I comprehend the English Grade 10 curriculum guide.	3.38	0.59	Average Quality of Delivery
Teaching/ Assessment	I assess whether my students meet learning objectives and adjust my teaching accordingly.	3.32	0.47	Average Quality of Delivery
Total		3.53	0.50	High Quality of Delivery

Legend:

High exposure	3.50-4.00
Average exposure	2.50-3.49
Inadequate exposure	1.50-2.49
Low exposure	1.00-1.49

Table 3 shows the fidelity of implementation of the Grade 10 English teachers in terms of quality of delivery. Data shows that the sample teachers were found to have the highest quality of delivery in ethics ($x = 3.82$), along with other usual teaching aspects including classroom environment ($x = 3.64$), and inclusivity, methods and strategies, and instructional delivery ($x=3.58$). It can be noted that teachers scored low in curriculum understanding ($x = 3.45$ & 3.38) pertaining to understanding the subject matter and the contents of the Grade 10 English curriculum guide with the Most Essential Learning Competencies. Palestina (2020) found that the teachers' commitment is vital in successfully implementing the curriculum. Lack of support in improving the teachers' workload was found to

negatively affect the efforts in curriculum. Time constraints were also referred to as factors which hinder the delivery of the curriculum due to the teachers' other non-teaching responsibilities. In other education systems, insufficient teacher training was also found to have resulted in poor curriculum implementation (Kimosop, 2018; Guerrero, 2019, and Rahman et al., 2019).

6.5. Curriculum fidelity of implementation and other demographic profile

It was found that public and private schools have average adherence to the curriculum. Lower teaching positions have higher adherence mean scores as compared to their higher teaching position counterparts. The adherence scores of private schools were found to have dismal differences as compared to private schools.

Further, it was found that there is a significant difference between the NAT scores and curriculum FOI in terms of adherence. No significant differences were found between NAT scores with exposure and quality of delivery. Haramain (2018) established that there are desirable factors that are attributed to a school's leading performance: person, school, student, and community-related factors which make up a holistic school community. In the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) 2018 results, the Philippine top performing schools in the said international assessment attributed their success to a student-centric environment which involved professional development of teachers. Peer mentoring among the students was likewise encouraged to allow competent learners to help their academically struggling classmates (Fababaer & Arboleda, DepEd Updates on Education Quality Press Conference, 2018).

When asked if there are certain desirable factors which the high performing schools conduct to attain fidelity of implementation, the sample teacher participants mentioned that they are given utmost priority in terms of specific feedback in classroom observations, upper hand in collaborative planning, and focus on student learning outcomes. It was also evident in the focus group discussions that the lowest performing schools conduct the same activities but are not as consistent as the top performing schools in the region. Factors such as lack of guidance from school heads and proper and strategic planning, which some teachers admitted also influence their fidelity of implementation, were also pointed as reasons for insufficient curricular implementation. Meno (1997, cited in Haramain, 2018) established that school administrators' leadership preparation and credentials influence teacher performance in the workplace.

In terms of their teaching experiences, teachers point to many reasons why they were not able to finish the expected learning competencies. These included learners' lack of foundational skills, impact of the CoVid-19 pandemic, lack of professional development seminars/workshops/write-shops on curriculum, teacher absenteeism, weather conditions, and teachers' lack of understanding of the *most* essential learning competencies.

6.6. Fidelity of implementation for curriculum delivery framework

The Fidelity of Implementation (FOI) for Curriculum Delivery Framework focuses on three dimensions: fidelity to curriculum standards, fidelity to teaching time and fidelity to lesson delivery. It is developed for teachers to better understand their curricular understanding, teaching practices, and curriculum delivery.

Figure 1.

Figure 1: Fidelity of Implementation for Curriculum Delivery Framework

Curriculum Fidelity of Implementation, in this framework, refers to the extent to which the curriculum is implemented as designed for curriculum delivery. This design is based on the learning competencies and standards set in a national curriculum. In the case of this study, the English Language Curriculum set the learning competencies and standards.

The Fidelity of Implementation (FOI) for Curriculum Delivery Framework focuses on three dimensions: fidelity to curriculum standards, fidelity to teaching time and fidelity to lesson delivery. Fidelity of Implementation, in this study, refers to the implementation of dimensions in the classroom. Figure 5 shows the framework and the relationships between and among the dimensions. The teacher characteristics, student engagement and student performance are connected through dotted lines to show their non-linear relationship with FOI for curriculum delivery.

In the fidelity to curriculum standards dimension, the learning competencies are expected to be fully implemented as stated in the curriculum. This refers to covering all the stated lessons under each competency. To gain high fidelity scores, teachers need to be aware of teaching all lessons expected to be covered in an academic year. This enables learners to benefit from a quality learning environment leading to increased student outcomes. Based on the study, it was found that high performing schools have teachers with high fidelity of implementation scores in national tests.

Fidelity to teaching time refers to teachers' FOI of the time allotment required for the subject. This is standard lesson time for the Philippine curriculum and is explicitly stated in the curriculum guide. Fidelity to teaching time is necessary for teachers to comply to cover the learning competencies required for the academic year. This also refers to covering all the time required for covering the lessons and written in teachers' lesson plans. Measuring fidelity to teaching time can be validated through classroom observations, interviews, presentation of lesson plans and teacher performance ratings.

The fidelity to lesson delivery dimension points to aspects of teaching that impacts student learning outcomes. This includes careful and strategic lesson planning and alignment of lesson objectives with the curricular objectives, and teaching strategies to engage learners. When teachers carefully design their lessons and are able to execute these properly in the classroom, the lesson delivery is more meaningful. Likewise, lesson planning must also foster interactive student engagement and provide assessments in line with the lessons.

Fidelity to lesson delivery means that teachers are able to put into good use their knowledge, skills, and values in the classroom. Their understanding of the curriculum is observable as they incorporate instructional strategies, select appropriate learning resources, and cater to the needs of their learners. These embody a deep understanding of how the curriculum is implemented. Fidelity to lesson delivery is the most observable dimension under this framework. It can be easily verified with classroom observations, analysis of teachers' lesson plans and classroom assessments.

This dimension also covers how teachers, at different career levels, show their mastery and expertise of the subject matter regardless of their demographics. This dimension can also strengthen teachers' fidelity scores in the two dimensions. As teachers deeply understand the curriculum and as they engage and delve into professional learning engagements, their fidelity to lesson delivery can improve.

The dimensions are inter-related with one another as teachers implemented the curriculum fidelity of implementation dimensions cohesively with one another. Their main goal in implementing these dimensions is to gain fidelity to achievement of student learning outcomes as shown in the framework. To measure the curriculum fidelity of implementation dimensions, the curriculum has to be identified. All supplemental documents must be readily accessible to be verified with a survey-questionnaire. This survey-questionnaire specifies all the curricular learning competencies to which teachers would respond to gain the dimension scores. Also, supplemental documents can be employed as means of verification for the dimension scores. These can be textbooks, lesson plans and classroom observation ratings which can support the numerical scores in the survey-questionnaire questions. It is important to analyze the curriculum fidelity of implementation scores through further validation by qualified raters. Focus group discussions can also be conducted to allow opportunities for follow-through of the dimension scores. For instance, a teacher scored high in the fidelity to curriculum standards but certain classroom details may surface during a focus group discussion such as extracurricular activities that take time off from actual teaching. There may also be circumstances where teachers gain high scores in one dimension but lesser in another. This can be addressed with caveats to understand that curriculum fidelity of implementation is not a linear process but rather relational with the other dimensions.

Generally, the curriculum fidelity of implementation framework is intended for teachers to better understand their curricular understanding, teaching practices, and curriculum delivery. This enables the researcher to understand how students achieved their learning outcomes through their teachers' lenses. What curriculum fidelity of implementation seeks to answer is why teachers teach the way they do as they implement the curriculum.

7. Implications

Based on the findings, the following implications were drawn:

1. Teacher demographics which are deemed traditionally associated with successful implementation do not often translate in most classrooms such as educational attainment, years of teaching experience, and teaching position.
2. Challenges with time management and planning can also have an impact on how faithfully teachers conduct their lessons in terms of exposure. English teachers teaching Grade 10 may underestimate how long an activity or conversation would take, which could result in hurried ends to classes or incomplete assignments.
3. Unexpected disruptions like assemblies, fire drills, or other school-related activities might cause timing errors and disrupt the lesson's flow. Furthermore, finding devoted time for thorough lesson planning can

be challenging due to restricted planning time, such as heavy teacher responsibilities, which could result in unforeseen time management problems in the classroom.

4. Curriculum FOI scores of teachers are related to their schools' national achievement scores. Teachers from high performing schools have higher curriculum FOI scores than teachers from low performing schools in the region.
5. Students' performance is a reliable indicator of how teachers faithfully implement the curriculum. Academic achievement is heavily influenced by implementation fidelity, but there are many other elements that also play a substantial role. These include resource availability, teacher effectiveness, and student motivation. These aspects underscore the complex nature of educational success.
6. Teachers experience several instructional concerns that directly affect their curriculum fidelity of implementation scores.

8. Conclusions

The following recommendations are drawn based on the study:

1. Curriculum fidelity of implementation measures can also be incorporated into teachers' performance ratings to provide evidence-based technical assistance to their teaching needs. Teachers may have understood the intent of the curriculum but have no means of being mentored or coached on how they can proceed forward in their teaching concerns.
2. Schools can benchmark with high performing schools, visit their English classrooms, and participate in academic discourses on how they can improve their own fidelity of implementation.
3. It is recommended that teachers are given technical and constant assistance in the implementation of the English curriculum standards through the Most Essential Learning Competencies through their school and/or division seminar-workshops to enable them to fully understand what constitutes "essential" competencies in their classes. It is likewise important to provide them with specific feedback especially for entry-level and novice teachers. Similarly, data play an important role in understanding the fidelity of implementation of English teachers in alignment with the curriculum.
4. With the number of school programs and projects that the Department requires from schools, it is recommended that hybrid learning, the combination of face-to-face classes and online learning, be fully institutionalized. This can contribute to the increase of time-on-task or contact time of teachers and implement all the needed competencies expected for the grade level.
5. Future researchers can also probe on the FOI implementation of teachers in other subjects, in the K to 12 full curriculum in order to have baseline data on the new and incoming MATATAG curriculum to be implemented by the Department of Education.

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